

How do teachers scaffold speaking activities in A2/B1 classroom?

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Word count: 3210

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**Verification pro forma for the Coursework Portfolio
Lesson Observations**

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 Course dates: January 2019 - July 2019

Lesson	Organisation	Class Identification	Time observed	Date observed	No. of Students	Signature of verifying teacher
1	EFA	Elementary	9:30-10:30	30.04.2019	5	<i>[Signature]</i>
2	EFA	Inter.	10:45-11:45	30.04.2019	6	<i>[Signature]</i>
3	EFA	Inter.	9:30-10:30	2.05.2019	10	<i>[Signature]</i>
4	EFA	Inter	10:45-11:45	2.05.2019	10	<i>[Signature]</i>
5	EFA	Inter	9:30-10:30	6.05.2019	5	<i>[Signature]</i>
6	EFA	Inter	10:45-11:45	6.05.2019	5	<i>[Signature]</i>
7	EFA	Inter	9:30-10:30	4.06.2019	5	<i>[Signature]</i>
8	EFA	Pre-Inter	10:45-11:45	4.06.2019	5	<i>[Signature]</i>
9	EFA	Pre-Inter	9:30-10:30	10.06.2019	9	<i>[Signature]</i>
10	EFA	Inter	10:45-11:45	10.06.2019	7	<i>[Signature]</i>

Comment as necessary

Part 1. Background

1.1 Rationale and goals

I am teaching primary students in Hong Kong. The issue of reticent speakers is quite prominent here. What I see as an engaging speaking activity often does not continue longer than a few minutes. Teacher-initiated discussions are also rarely met with enthusiasm. I used to believe in a stereotype that Asian people are more reserved due to some socio-cultural factors and almost ceased my attempts to make them talk.

However, the survey by Zhang and Head (2016) helped me overcome this misconception. It clearly showed that Chinese students could be as proactive and outgoing as others, but it requires the teacher's awareness and conscious effort. Eliminating the fear of failure, designing achievable and appealing tasks, providing some prompts are just a few conditions that make it possible.

Speaking is a complex phenomenon and is deeply affected by one's personality. Many people find it intimidating to talk within a group of people, even in their mother tongue. Thus, providing learners speaking opportunities might be insufficient without considering the multiple factors that affect their desire and ability to speak. Speaking is a transient act which means it co-occurs with thinking. Deciding on what to say and how to say presents a significant challenge for learners. A teacher can help by doing more behind-the-scenes work, which I refer to as 'scaffolding' in my project.

I am highly interested to know how teachers address scaffolding in their practice, how they set the speaking tasks, what they do to create an atmosphere conducive to speaking, and whether they provide their learners the necessary support. To find it out, I plan to create an observation form that will embrace the variety of means teachers use to facilitate students' talk during their lessons. I hope this project will help me expand my toolbar of techniques and make me more efficient in teaching speaking.

Overall, I pursue the following goals in my project:

Goal 1 To experiment with instrument design.

Goal 2 To find out what scaffolding techniques teachers use and which of them I could apply to my teaching.

Goal 3 To become more efficient as an observer.

1.2 Literature review and the initial instrument design

Definition of scaffolding

ELT authors understand the concept of scaffolding quite broadly. Drawing on the Vygotskian idea of ZPD (1978), Wood, Bruner, and Ross (1976) see scaffolding as the set of the activities provided by the educator, or more competent peer, to support the students as they move through the zone of proximal development. Thornbury (2005) paraphrases scaffolding as the supportive framework provided by somebody with better knowledge. Regarding the speaking activities, the following examples can be attributed as scaffolding: a teacher reminds learners what to include in their answer, helps them generate ideas, asks some guiding questions, models the answer, helps learners plan their answer, provides or elicits related vocabulary on the board.

In my research, I have complimented the idea of scaffolding with some of Dörnyei's five elements of a safe speaking environment: appropriate timing, genuine peer interactions, collaborative tasks, meaningful feedback, and student-selected topics (2018).

Peer interaction

Vygotsky (1978) views interaction with peers as an effective way of developing speaking skills. He believes that learning occurs when learners share knowledge through social interaction, which suggests that a 'learner to learner' setting is more valuable in terms of communication than a 'teacher-learner' one.

Curry (2018) believes that learners exhibit a much greater complexity in their language and are willing to experiment with language, take risks, and make mistakes in peer interaction. Long (1983) reaches a similar conclusion by contrasting 'learner to learner' and 'learner to native speaker' modes of communication. His study shows that the learners talked longer with other learners than they did with native speakers.

Feedback

Nevertheless, a significant amount of classroom communication takes place within a teacher-student setting. In this regard, the teacher talk has the potential to affect the learners' performance. A view on the teacher as a 'facilitator of communication' (Clifton: 2006) attributes great importance to the teacher's feedback. Ur (1997) argues that it is unfair to ask students to put much effort into something and then disregard the result. To address this, I have included three forms of feedback in my instrument, e.g., error correction, general feedback, and praise.

Some scholars believe that error correction does more harm than good. Excessive error correction 'destroys' speaking (Harmer: 1991). Nunan urges teachers to highly limit their interventions instead of focusing on communication rather than grammatical accuracy (1999). Focusing on form more than on meaning teachers might demotivate students and add to their reluctance to speak (Walsh: 2006).

Timing

Dörnyei (2018) suggests that a foreign language classroom easily creates anxiety which inhibits speaking. My experience suggests that language teachers often overlook this point. A conventional practice of nominating students immediately after setting a question increases the affective filter. Kerr argues that allowing students sufficient time for task completion, including some time for a 'mental rehearsal', accommodates the mental comfort of the learners (2017). Lavery suggests that allowing students to discuss with their peers before talking to the whole class eliminates a lot of pressure (2009).

Pre-task

Lavery (2009) argues that sufficient preparation is crucial for task success. Teachers need to make sure that students understand the instructions and possess the necessary lexical and topical knowledge; also, they should break the task into small parts and provide a model answer. This view induced me to divide each activity into stages.

Nation is positive that teachers should adjust the oral tasks to suit their students' communicative ability (2000) by differentiating the objectives, time, and content. I included differentiation in the preparation stage. Only by setting manageable tasks and realistic expectations can teachers hope for success.

Interest

The genuine interest in finding out factual information about their peers boosts students participation in the task, resulting in more extended conversations (Dörnyei: 2018). Thus, teachers should ask more referential and open-ended questions to promote meaning-focused communication.

According to Nation (2000), teachers can enhance meaningful communication by setting free production tasks, where learners, for instance, share experiences or discuss their opinions. At the same time, Ur points out that controlled activities are unavoidable and justifiable at a low level of language proficiency. This view prompted me to include semi-controlled activities in my observations. For example, a free activity: 'Discuss in pairs your views on being vegetarian' can be redesigned in a more structured task: 'With your partner provide two arguments for and against being vegetarian using the following discourse markers.'

Initial instrument

Characteristics of the activity			Before the activity					During the activity		After the activity	
Type of activity	Mode of interaction S-S, T-S, SS-SS	Free/controlled / Semi-controlled	Pre-task activity	T provides a visual/verbal demonstration; elicits the stages necessary for the task completion	T allows preparation time	T checks understanding	T differentiates activity	Error correction (on the spot/delayed/none)	Questions T asks (referential/open-ended)	T praises SS	T gives feedback

1.3 Teachers' profile and ethics

I conducted my observations at the institution which serves as an official DipTesol course provider in Hong Kong. The three teachers I observed are qualified at the diploma level and have over ten years of experience teaching General English adult classes.

No protocol issues occurred during the observations. I did not ask the observed teachers to alter their behavior to satisfy the needs of this project. Thus, no abuse of authority took place. I had post-observation discussions with the teachers to ensure the adequacy of interpretation. Pursuing confidentiality, I did not mention the teachers' names in my research.

Part 2. Evolution of the instrument

2.1 First set of observations and instrument 1.2

The first peer observation experience became a challenge for me as I often struggled to attribute the teachers' actions to a particular box. I had to make many notes which distracted me from the actual observation. Further analysis of these notes clearly showed that my form lacked focus. The number and the variety of criteria made observations difficult. With twelve columns, the form looked cluttered. The second instrument benefited from the removal of three columns. Also, it became apparent that my understanding of scaffolding overlapped with motivation and needed a better focus.

<u><i>Rationale</i></u>	<u><i>Changes made</i></u>
Fully controlled activities were not observed.	Excluded.
The teachers did not allow students preparation time.	Deleted.
No preparatory work was done.	'Pre-task' deleted.
'T provides a visual/verbal demonstration; elicits the lexis necessary for the task completion' was wordy.	Divided into two boxes, 'T pre-teaches lexis' and 'T provides examples'.
No error correction was observed during the lessons.	Deleted but still can be registered in the 'feedback' box.
Contrasting open-ended and referential questions was not effective, as they are not opposites.	Deleted, yet, 'T asks questions' retained.
'During' and 'after' activity stages overlap.	Merged.
The teachers did not differentiate the task content and instructions according to the students' level.	Deleted.
'T praises SS' was too ambiguous.	Embraced into 'T provides encouragement' box.
The teachers often expressed their approval by non-linguistic means.	'T provides encouragement by verbal/non-verbal means' was added.

The decision to distinguish verbal and non-verbal encouragement was inspired by one of the observees, who used a lot of miming, gestures, and facial expressions. It facilitated a positive and relaxing environment in the class. Ur argues that nodding, smiling, and echoing can make the speaker feel they are saying something worthwhile and enhance their willingness to speak (Ur: 2015).

Instrument 1.2

Characteristics of the activity			Before the activity			During or after the activity		
Type of activity	Mode of interaction S-S, T-S, SS-SS	Free / Semi-controlled	T pre-teaches lexis required for the task completion	T provides examples	T checks understanding	T asks questions	T provides encouragement by verbal/non-verbal means	T gives feedback

2.2 Second set of observations and instrument 1.3

In my previous attempt, I observed two teachers for one lesson each. This time I observed two lessons taught by the same teacher, which yielded more consistent results.

<u><i>Rationale</i></u>	<u><i>Changes made</i></u>
Defining the 'type' of the activity required extra time but had little value for the analysis.	Substituted with numbers.
'T asks questions' was not specific.	The distinction between referential and display questions was made.
No modelling was done.	'T provides examples' deleted.
The teacher did not feed in lexis for the task.	Deleted.
The teacher helped students produce utterances via non-linguistic means.	'T elicits answers from students by giving them visual/verbal clues' was added.
The teacher provided corrective feedback occasionally, it prompted me to measure the amount of it.	'T provides feedback on form/meaning' added.
The teacher regularly checked the clarity of instructions with their learners.	ICQs were added alongside with CCQs.
I had to fit my comments into the margins around the form.	An extra box on the bottom was designed.
The activities observed were relatively short and fast, the staging was redundant.	Chunking of activity into periods was cancelled.

My third instrument allows me to collect the data for the quantitative analysis. The assumption was that in a modern communicative classroom, the features of facilitator talk prevail (Clifton: 2006).

Instrument 1.3

	Activity 1	Activity 2	Activity 3	Activity 4	Activity 5	Activity 6
Mode of interaction S-S, SS-SS, T-S						
Nature of activity, free/semi-controlled F / S-C						
T elicits answers from students by giving them verbal/ visual clues Verb / Vis/ both						
T encourages SS by verbal/non-verbal means V/ N-V/ both						
T asks display or referential questions D / R/ both						
T checks the understanding CCQ / ICQ/ both						
T provides feedback on form/meaning F / M/ both						
Comments						

2.3 Analysis of the data collected with instrument 1.3

I have visualized the data collected with my third instrument during six hours of observation with three different teachers in the bar chart below.

The institution I observed executed the traditional teacher-fronted layout of the classroom. Most communication happened between teachers and students. Group work and pair work were relatively unemployed, which generally reduced student speaking opportunities.

- The proportion of free activities significantly outweighed the semi-controlled ones. However, a few times when pre-intermediate students were assigned a free speaking task, they appeared frustrated and struggled to carry on the conversation. The above suggests that more structured tasks can be advantageous with low proficiency students.

- Visual prompts were almost as popular as verbal ones. When students failed to understand the verbal clues, the teacher's miming helped them guess the word and continue the task.
- Teachers primarily provided verbal encouragement to their students. Some teachers used many gestures and facial expressions, while others preferred not to use body language. The female teachers, in general, behaved more empathetically, were keeping an eye-contact and smiling. Observing the group activities, the female teachers were standing within close proximity, actively listening and nodding. Also, they reacted fast if they saw a breakdown of communication. The male teacher, on the contrary, stood further away from the learners, rarely intervened, and generally looked less engaged in the lesson. A few times, learners failed to get the teacher's help when it was needed.
- Compared to the display questions, the referential questions were asked more frequently and elicited more enthusiasm from the learners. The teachers who were overusing the display questions received shorter replies from the learners.
- CCQs were uncommon. The teachers were mainly concerned about the clarity of the instructions.
- A tendency to comment more on the content than on form benefited the atmosphere of genuine communication at the lesson. Building on the teacher's feedback, students produced much emergent language.

As a general observation, student speaking time overweighed the teacher speaking time; teachers' interventions were moderate. However, the teachers did not always attentively monitor the classroom dynamics and sometimes failed to provide the necessary support. Lively conversations occurred between stronger students, while the weaker ones often looked puzzled and struggled to talk.

Part 3. Final instrument and evaluation

3.1 Rethinking of scaffolding and the final instrument

It has been two years since the last instrument was created and tested. After doing the Diploma course teaching practice, I had a few insights into teaching speaking. I realized that instructions are not a priori clear to the learners, which sometimes might be fatal for the task. The active task-stacking is counter-productive as it makes learners rush through the activities. The unbalanced timing deprives students of maximizing their experiences and stretching their potentials during the task. The new knowledge and expertise made me redesign the final instrument.

Also, I reevaluated my approach to the instrument design. The observed context largely shaped the three versions of the instrument presented above. When in fact, some scaffolding elements missing from the observed classroom did not make them irrelevant and should not prevent me from including them in my instrument.

<u><i>Rationale</i></u>	<u><i>Changes made</i></u>
Verbal means of elicitation are not compared in terms of effectiveness with visual ones.	Deleted.
Encouragement and praise are crucial for motivation but not directly linked to scaffolding.	Deleted.
Concept checking does not necessarily take the form of a question.	Reworded.

Display questions are not compared in terms of effectiveness with referential ones.	Deleted.
The importance of instruction checking was not reflected in the previous form.	ICQs were given a separate box.
There was no space to note the class particulars.	An extra box on the top was added.
Feedback is generally more relevant to motivation than scaffolding.	Deleted; feeding forward was emphasized instead.

<u>Boxes added</u>	<u>Rationale</u>
Meaningful task	A task should resemble a real-life situation and enable students to make use of their authentic experiences.
Close proximity	Ongoing close monitoring of the class enables a teacher to provide repair or feed in the language during the task.
Modelling	Most learners find seeing an example more effective than explanation.
Timing	Time should be sufficient for learners to prepare, complete, and repeat the task if needed. Students produce more output during the second attempt.
T feeds in lexis and grammar before the task	T ensures learners are equipped with the linguistics resources that might be useful for task completion.
T elicits ideas from students	It activates students' background knowledge, triggers imagination, helps struggling students.
Concept checking stage	Students should be clear about the language point taught, its use, and meaning before doing the task.

Final instrument

Date:	Time:	Class:		Teacher:		Number of students:	
		Activity 1	Activity 2	Activity 3	Activity 4	Activity 5	
Mode of interaction S-S, T-S (student-student, teacher-student)							
Nature of activity F / SC (free/semi-controlled)							
Meaningful task							
T delivers a concept check							
T elicits ideas from SS							
T feeds in lexis and grammar point helpful for the task							
T models the answer							
T checks the understanding of instructions							
T sets appropriate timing							
T stands close to the students/ T monitors break out rooms							
Comments							

3.2 Conclusion

A two-year gap between the start and the end of the project allows me to register my professional development process. The evolution of the instrument reflects the evolution of my views on teaching speaking. Starting with a quite vague idea of scaffolding in the first instrument, I have gradually gained a more concrete and practical vision. Interestingly, the process was partly cyclical. For example, the timing and modeling included in the early instruments were deleted at one point and then restored in the final version. Diploma teaching practice made me rethink some other scaffolding elements and convinced me that one activity thoroughly done by the learners and carefully scaffolded by the teacher is worth a series of 'rushed' ones.

Experimenting with instrument design, I have learnt that less is more. Including a great variety of observation criteria in the earlier versions of the instrument proved to be obstructive to the observation process. The fewer features enabled me to observe more precisely. I find the final instrument better focused, laid out, and more convenient than the previous editions. I also find it suitable both for peer observation and self-assessment purposes. It provides a helpful checklist for teachers allowing them to monitor the degree of scaffolding in their lessons. The scaffolding elements included in the last version are quite common for a communicative classroom, making the form widely applicable.

A tick-box format helps an observer concentrate on the observation process rather than on filling in the form. As long as there is a comment box at the bottom of each column, an observer might use a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches to data collection. Alternatively, the form can be easily adapted for a descriptive observation as the boxes provide enough space for writing notes.

The project showed me the value peer observation has for one's professional development. Both observers and observees benefit from it. However, an observer should observe for not more than one area at a time. Also, observing with a form was more efficient in terms of time and quality. It made me think that creating a database of the observation instruments designed during the projects like this and making it public could contribute to the ELT field. Observing my colleagues, I had many insights about my teaching; I learnt how to use this tool for reflection and self-betterment. The project helped me become a more attentive and thoughtful observer than I used to be.

Overall, the project had a positive impact on my teaching. I have accumulated a collection of practical scaffolding tips through reading, observing, and reflecting during the project, which enabled me to deliver speaking activities more productively.

References:

1. Clifton, J. (2006). Facilitator talk. *ELT Journal*, Volume 60(2), pp.142–50.
2. Curry, N. (2018). *Developing Speaking Skills in the ELT Classroom*. [webinar]. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Br4nxGcvh48&feature=youtu.be> [Accessed 17 June 2019]
3. Dörnyei, Z. (2018). *Safe Speaking Environments*. [webinar]. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-wDmI-DUt-c&t=1294s> [Accessed 17 June 2019]
4. Harmer, J. (1991). *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. The 3rd Edition. London and New York: Longman.
5. Kerr, P. (2017). *Time for Speaking*. [webinar]. Available at: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J_aex5istbU&feature=youtu.be [Accessed 17 June 2019]
6. Lavery, C. (2009) *Reluctant talkers 1*. [Blog] Teaching English. Available at: <http://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/article/reluctant-talkers-1> [Accessed 17 June 2019]
7. Lightbown P., Spada, N. (2006). *How languages are learned*. The 3rd edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
8. Long, M. (1983). 'Native and non-native speaker conversation and the negotiation of comprehensible input'. *Applied Linguistics*, Volume 4(2), pp. 126-41.
9. Nation, I.S.P. (2000). Creating, adapting and using language teaching techniques. *English Language Institute Occasional Publication*, Volume 20. Victoria University of Wellington.
10. Nunan, D. (1999). *Second Language Teaching and Learning*. Boston: Heinle and Heinle Publisher.
11. Thornbury, S. (2010). *S is for scaffolding*. [Blog] A-Z blog. Available at: <https://scotthornbury.wordpress.com/2010/04/04/s-is-for-scaffolding/> [Accessed 17 June 2019]
12. Ur, P. (1997). *Discussions that work*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
13. Ur P. (2015). *Getting them to talk in English (when they don't want to)*. [webinar]. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tCWs6RQEzNY&feature=youtu.be> [Accessed 17 June 2019]
14. Vygotsky, L. (1978). *Mind in society: the development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
15. Walsh S. (2006) Talking the talk of the TESOL classroom, *ELT Journal*, Volume 60(2).
16. Wood, D. J., Bruner, J. S., & Ross, G. (1976). The Role of Tutoring in Problem Solving. *Journal of Child Psychiatry and Psychology*, Volume 17, pp. 89-100
17. Zhang, X., Head, K. (2010) Dealing with learner reticence in the speaking class, *ELT Journal*, Volume 64 (1)

Appendix. Examples of data gathering process

T. Eve SS: A1/A2, 5 Date: 30th Apr. 9:30-10:30 T shows up, wags head, smile!

Characteristics of the activity			Before the activity					During the activity		After the activity	
Type of activity	Mode of interaction S-S, T-S, SS-SS	Free/controlled/Semi-controlled	Pre-task activity	T provides a visual/verbal demonstration; elicits the stages necessary for the task completion	T allows preparation time	T checks understanding	T differentiates activity	Error correction (on the spot/delayed/ none)	Questions T asks (referential/open-ended)	T praises SS	T gives feedback
What good places to eat you know in Shenyang?	S-S	F	no	no	-	are tomatoes always red?	no	no	Do you know what I like?	no	no
T shows picture cards elicits vocab from SS	T-S	S/C	n/a	-	-	Can we drink dressing?	-	no	-	gestures, face expression	Good job
WS complete the dialogue: what would you like on your salad?	S-S	S/C	n/a	-	yes	Do u need to speak or to write?	-	no	-	puts hand on the board	gives comments
Substitutional drill: Can I have? Would u like?	T-S	S/C	n/a	Puts fly model phrases on the board	n/a	-	-	recall	-	Smiles, wags head, keeps eye contact	-
Role play: customer shop assistant	S-S	S/C	yes	Two SS run the activity in front of the class	-	Do u need to write?	-	Delayed, after task T puts on board	yes	yes	yes
2nd run of the role play	S-S	S/C	no	T gave comments on the 1st run	-	-	-	-	-	yes	no

check up vocab at the end

2nd run - much more confident

T adds up new vocab.

(1)

T: Sean

SS: B1/B2, 10

Date: 2nd May, 9:45-10:45

3

Characteristics of the activity			Before the activity			During or after the activity		
Type of activity	Mode of interaction S-S, T-S, SS-SS	Free / Semi-controlled	T pre-teaches lexis required for the task completion	T provides examples	T checks understanding	T asks questions	T provides encouragement by verbal/non-verbal means	T gives feedback on errors
Guessing - work out the words from the pictures	T-S	F	✓	n/a	✓	✓	✓	n/a
Talk about street life in HK (+, -)	T-SS	F	n/a	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
Questions practicing	T-SS	s/c	n/a	X	✓	✓	✓	X
Filling in the questionnaire	SS-SS	F	n/a	X	✓	n/a	n/a	✓
Talking about the pictures	SS-SS	F	X	X	X	✓	✓	X
Talk to your partner about the words you've heard	SS-SS	F	X	X	✓	X	✓	X

compound nouns -
stages of
scaffolding

Why did I put "crosses" in the middle-
CCQ

T: Sean

SS: 5

Pre-Inter time: 10:45-11:45

Date: 4.06.2019

	Activity 1	Activity 2	Activity 3	Activity 4	Activity 5	Activity 6	
Mode of interaction S-S, SS-SS, T-S	S-S	T-S	T-S	S-S	T-S	T-S	ad of SSS
Nature of activity, free/semi-controlled, controlled F / S-C	F	F	S-C	S-C	S-C	S-C	F
T elicits answers from students by giving them verbal/ visual clues Verb / Vis/ both	both	both	Verb	Vis.	w/a	w/a	n/o
T encourages SS by verbal/non-verbal means V / N-V/ both	both	both	V	V	V	-	-
T asks display or referential questions D / R/ both	R	D	D	both	D	D	-
T checks the understanding CCQ / ICQ/ both	ICQ	w/a	CCQ	ICQ	w/a	ICQ	ICQ
T provides feedback on form/meaning F / M/ both	M	F	F	F	F	F	both
Comments	How to you relax	Put vocab on board, verb + noun collocation	Making examples	WS to fill in gaps	checking the answers	WS + check. The answer	check SS around what they like to do to relax

T gives students opportunity to speak by keeping silent and using body lang. (8)